

Open data tools to combat Ebola

Description

In 2014, the world's largest Ebola outbreak occurred in West Africa, and quickly spread primarily through the countries of Sierra Leone, Guinea, and Liberia. Its rapid transmission was fuelled in part by traditional burial practices that saw family and friends of the deceased put at increased risk of infection. Furthermore, limited information sharing between neighbouring countries along with relatively open and unpatrolled borders aided the spread of the disease.

Through the sharing of open data between countries and international bodies like the United Nations and the World Food Program, data analytics proved to be a vital component of the containment of the outbreak. When first declared, the outbreak was predicted to kill approximately 100,000 people worldwide and cost over \$1 billion to contain.

The National Ebola Response Centre served as vital infrastructure for gathering and disseminating data to primary decision makers and coordinating the efforts of multiple international organisations and countries directly impacted. The Humanitarian Data Exchange (HDX) housed datasets related to the number of health-care workers infected, the location of safe and dignified burial teams, the status and location of Ebola Community Care Centres, and much more. HDX allowed all team members to have access to the same validated data simultaneously. Finally, GeoNode, an open source geo-spatial platform, enabled access to datasets including administrative boundaries in affected countries, transportation and logistics information, and geo-tagged health crisis data.

Economic benefits

Large scale epidemics generally impact all aspects of society and influence the price of food stuffs. Using the HDX, teams were able to track the spread of the virus through

monitoring the price of important crops, including rice and other staples. Where price would increase it would generally indicate an outbreak as there were fewer people involved in food production due to sickness or care of a relative. Stopping the spread of the Ebola virus saved not only direct costs related to treatment and prevention but also stabilised local and national economies, preventing inflation, price gouging and other negative impacts for those not directly infected with the disease.

Health/social benefits

Open source data and data sharing platforms enabled local governments, international organisations and team members on the ground to work collaboratively to contain the Ebola virus as quickly as possible. These efforts resulted in countless lives saved. The crisis and use of analytical data also spurred a rapid uptake of open data by international organisations involved in the response along with the governments of affected countries, fuelling collaboration and collective problem solving.

Supporting links

<http://odim pact.org/case-battling-ebola-in-sierra-leone.html>

Accessed 14 May 2016.

'Ebola outbreak economics'

http://bit.ly/Ebola_Outbreak_Economics

Accessed 14 May 2016.

<http://ebolageonode.org/>

Accessed 14 May 2016.

'Data exchange helps humanitarians to act fast and

efficiently' http://bit.ly/Data_exchange_helps_humanitarians

Accessed 14 May 2016.